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4th International Congress on Food Safety and Quality ONE HEALTH

November 9th-12th, 2022 | Dubrovnik, Croatia

4th International Congress on Food Safety and Quality “One Health”

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Dear colleagues, dear friends,

It is my great honour and pleasure to invite you on behalf of the Organising and Scientific Committee to participate in the 4th International Congress on Food Safety and Quality under the slogan “One Health”, which will be held in Dubrovnik, from 9 to 12 November 2022.

The International Congress on Food Safety and Quality will again be held under the auspices of the competent authorities and institutions and is organised by the Andrija Štampar Teaching Institute of Public Health, the Croatian Metrology Society, and the Southeast European Food Quality and Safety Control Network (SEEN-FSQC). The co-organisers are the Faculty of Agriculture and the Faculty of Food Technology and Biotechnology, the University of Zagreb, the Institute for Health and Food Safety Zenica, and the Institute of Public Health of Vojvodina, in cooperation with other eminent institutions from the country and abroad.

Thanks to the extremely important topics and the esteemed experts who shared their knowledge and experiences with us at the first three Congresses on Food Safety and Quality, we were all happy to see

truly great interest: the Congresses New Achievements and Future Challenges in 2017, Food Life Cycle in 2018, and Food, Health and Climate Change in 2020 were attended by nearly 1,000 participants, while numerous guest speakers from the country and the world presented their colourful presentations in the form of exceptional plenary lectures, excellent oral presentations, satellite symposia, workshops, and posters. On the wings of these successes, our goal is to organise an even more significant, distinctive, and educational 4th International Congress on Food Safety and Quality.

We will present the significant experiences of domestic and foreign experts in the field of food counterfeiting, protection of the origin and geographical origin of food, and new, exact analytical achievements in this field.

Food safety and quality, determination of food origin and geographical origin, adulteration of food and its impact on consumer health, as well as the impact of climate change on farming and quality are all topics of crucial significance and impose a shared responsibility on all stakeholders in the food production chain. These are primarily countries, producers, distributors, consumers, but also the media, which are responsible for accurately reporting current topics to the public, including this very relevant issue.

Given that our common task is not only to protect, but also to improve the health of each of our residents, by organising the 4th International Congress “One Health” we also want to continue to raise awareness of this important topic in the profession.

Thank you for your response.

Sincerely,
Prof Branko Kolarić, MD, PhD
Congress President

Dietary exposure assessment of Croatian consumers to ochratoxin A from coffee

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Coffee is one of the most popular beverages in Croatia. Coffee trees are planted in tropical and semi-tropical areas, but coffees are roasted worldwide. Coffee is prone to attacks by various fungi genus *Aspergillus* and *Penicillium* whose species synthesize ochratoxin A (OTA). Contamination of coffee beans with OTA depends on various factors such as fungus species and strain, water activity, processing conditions, storage, and transportation. The most significant impact is related to environmental and climate conditions. OTA can be present in coffee at a certain level, even when processors follow good agricultural practices (GAP). Therefore, GAP guidelines should be updated according to One Health principles. In order to assess the chronic dietary exposure of adult Croatian consumers to OTA in coffee beverages, occurrence data (n=55) derived from national monitoring 2015-2020 and consumption data (n=2002 respondents) from the National Survey on Food Consumption of the Adult Population in Croatia 2011-2012 were used. A total of 1649 consumers reported daily consumption, some even several times per day. For dietary exposure, an assessment a margin of exposure (MOE) approach was applied by use Benchmark Dose Level (BMDL₁₀) as referent point for neoplastic (14.5 µg/kg bw per day) and non-neoplastic (4.73 µg/kg bw per day) effects. Average dietary exposure of adult consumers does not exceed values within the Lower Bound (LB), Middle Bound (MB), and Upper Bound (UB) approach for both BMDL₁₀. The calculated MOE results for non-neoplastic effects (LB 24481.45; MB 15958.54; UB 11850.06) and for neoplastic effects (LB 75048.84; MB 48921.52; UB 36326.83) represents a low health concern.

KEY WORDS: climate; environment; food consumption; margin of exposure (MOE); One Health

Elemental composition and health risk of Fruška Gora wines

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The elements in wine could influence wine quality and safety – are there potential health risks for the consumers of Fruška gora wines? The elemental composition (23 elements) of 131 bottled dry wines, 113 (red, white, and rose) produced in 30 Fruška Gora wineries and 18 (red) from several European countries was obtained by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) analysis. The exposure of adult men and women was estimated taking into account wine consumption on population average, regular drinkers only, chronic heavy drinkers and level recommended by the Wine in moderation (WIM) for red wine. Related to Fruška gora wines, not one of the investigated elements/wines showed potential for non-carcinogenic risk [hazard quotients and index 10 for men and women, except at P95 in “WIM” scenario (Margin of exposure (MOE) >1, negligible risk)]. With respect to arsenic, evaluation of carcinogenic risk revealed a disagreement between MOE (mean and P95 MOE >10, no risk) and lifetime cancer risk approach (tolerable risk of 1 extra lifetime cancer case per 100,000 persons was exceeded across the exposure scenarios at P90, P75, P75, and P25 for males, and P75 and P50 in “heavy” and “WIM” scenarios for females). Comparison of red wines, Fruška gora vs. international, revealed no significant differences in estimated risk of arsenic, whereas Fruška Gora wines showed a statistically lower MOEs to lead. Apart from the risk assessment, the obtained elemental profiles could be a valuable resource in distinguishing wine geographical origin.

KEY WORDS: hazard index; food safety; ICP-MS; Lifetime Cancer Risk; margin of exposure

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